

FHERITALE

POLICY BRIEF

Research Infrastructures to Support Cross-Domain
Investigation on Micro- and Nanomaterials in Food, Health,
and the Environment

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Policy Brief

Research Infrastructures to Support Cross-Domain Investigation on Micro- and Nanomaterials in Food, Health, and the Environment

Project fact sheet

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-05 Preparation of common strategies for future development of RI technologies and services within broad RI communities

FHERITALE – Food, Health and Environment Research Infrastructures to Tackle Emerging Priorities <https://fheritale.eu>

FHERITALE overarching goal is preparing a roadmap for services to address the needs of research to investigate the impact on health and on the environment that a set of selected, prioritized artificial materials at the micro and nanoscale can have. Given the interdisciplinary nature of this research area, these services will span several domains, from health, food and environmental sciences.

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1. Background

Human activities, particularly industrialization and the widespread use of artificial materials, have significantly affected human, animal, and environmental health. These impacts have become increasingly urgent as industrial processes continue to accelerate. A key consequence is the massive waste generation, with the European Union alone producing 2,233 million tonnes of waste in 2022, highlighting the scale of human influence on the environment ([Statistics for the European Green Deal](#)). This waste contributes to pollution and worsens interconnected health issues, stressing the need for urgent action to address environmental degradation.

Despite growing research on such environmental and health impacts, knowledge gaps persist, partly due to a lack of standard definitions and measurement protocols. To understand the extent of these challenges, a "One Health" approach is critical ("One Health" is defined by the [One Health High-Level Expert Panel - OHHLEP](#) as an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems ; [Overview - European Commission](#)). Technology availability and service provision is fundamental and the availability of Research Infrastructures providing access to state-of-the-art technologies for addressing the aforementioned challenges that span Health, Environment and Food domains is key for advancing our understanding and research capabilities in this field. Achieving this successful integration necessitates careful consideration of several key aspects. Interdisciplinary collaboration is a cornerstone of this process, demanding the engagement of diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, to ensure that solutions are contextually appropriate and impactful.

The FHERITALE project aims to highlight these gaps by analyzing current literature on artificial materials at the micro- and nanoscale within the One Health framework. This includes identifying trends, clusters, and technological needs and making it possible through technological developments within research infrastructures to close such gaps.

2. Current state of development and implementation

During the initial eighteen months of the FHERITALE project, we launched into several networking activities. These efforts, bolstered by contributions from external experts, yielded significant results. Our goal was to thoroughly map current research on the health impact of artificial micro- and nanoparticles and provide the European research community with a comprehensive, cross-thematic overview of available services for key scientific priorities. This was implemented through an extensive bibliometric analysis to identify thematic priorities, which resulted in a database of over 800 papers providing a comprehensive overview of the current research landscape on micro- and nano-scale material particles, from the standpoint of the potential impact on health. This work, published in part on the ORE platform (<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20244.1>), highlighted the relations among the different research domains within the broad field addressed by FHERITALE and supported the identification of the most commonly used methodologies. The latter are relevant for the definition of services.

Following the circulation of a survey aiming at mapping services currently provided by national, regional or European infrastructures, a two-day strategic retreat in Utrecht was pivotal to strengthen collaboration and synergies with European RIs not part of the FHERITALE consortium and with other key stakeholders. The external experts who attended provided fertile background for collaborations, insight exchanges, and the shaping of strategic priorities (<https://fheritale.eu/fheritale-strategic-meeting-utrecht>). This made possible the development of an initial map of services currently available (<https://fheritale.eu/survey-outcomes>). This map represents the first seed of a cluster of RIs offering services. Indeed, it already includes services by Instruct-ERIC, AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, METROFOOD-RI, which are partners in the project, but also services offered by EuroBioImaging-ERIC, EMBRC-ERIC and MIRRI-ERIC.

A further extensive analysis of the aforementioned body of literature, complemented with a collection of papers resulting from CUSP projects, ISO, and other selected publications, led to a first draft of technologies currently used for research on key thematic priorities. After the definition of a Service Readiness Classification (SRC), these technologies were categorized based on their maturity in view of an uptake as services at the RI level. Tailored to FHERITALE's priorities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15554666>), the new technology table offers a dual benefit: it highlights current research strengths and constitutes a strategic roadmapping instrument. By prioritizing adaptability and future scalability over immediate readiness, it fosters a comprehensive, cross-thematic understanding of the technological landscape. This foundational work is essential for identifying gaps and implementing a strategic technology development roadmap in the subsequent project phase. Given their crucial role in promoting and enhancing the use of cutting-edge instrumentation, collaborative efforts among RIs on technology could lead to the development of innovative equipment and novel protocols, benefiting the entire community of current and potential new users engaged in micro- and nanoparticle research.

Finally, a white paper on key selected priorities (<https://zenodo.org/records/15222316>) outlined underlying challenges and gaps at various levels. One of the most pressing challenges identified was the lack of robust analytical and technological tools for studying micro- and nanoplastics. Current methodologies are fragmented, with no standardized samples or protocols across laboratories, making it difficult to compare results or ensure reproducibility. Detection technologies for nanoplastics, especially in complex biological and environmental matrices, remain underdeveloped. There is a strong need for non-destructive, quantitative tools and certified reference materials that can support accurate measurement and traceability. Additionally, computational modeling tools are essential to simulate exposure scenarios and better understand the behavior of these particles in real-world conditions.

Another major gap lies in the research and knowledge landscape, particularly regarding the biological and environmental impacts of artificial materials. The field suffers from inconsistent terminology due to its multidisciplinary nature, which hampers collaboration and data integration. While many studies focus on characterizing materials, fewer address mitigation strategies or practical applications such as bioremediation. Risk assessments, particularly in the food sector, are still insufficient, leaving critical questions about human health impacts unanswered.

3. Policy recommendations

Adopt a One Health Approach

Promote policies that integrate human, animal, and environmental health to address the complex impacts of artificial materials holistically.

Support Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Encourage collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders across health, environment, and food sectors to ensure contextually appropriate solutions.

Standardize Terminology and Protocols

Develop and enforce common definitions, measurement standards, and analytical protocols to improve data comparability and research reproducibility.

Enhance Technological Development

Support the development of non-destructive, quantitative tools and certified reference materials for accurate detection and analysis of nanoplastics.

Elucidate organism-MNP interactions

Promote the understanding of the biological mechanisms of interaction between organisms and micro and nanoparticles.

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